

Title: Towards creating an injury severity index for experimental traumatic brain injury (TBI): data-driven and knowledge-driven approaches

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Abstract

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) has the highest incidence of all neurological disorders, and is a major source of death and long-term disability worldwide. Yet the seemingly simple act of assessing TBI severity remains a major, unresolved challenge. Central to this problem is that TBI encompasses a broad class of heterogeneous injuries superimposed on the intrinsic complexity of the mammalian brain. From a biological perspective, TBI impacts multiple scales of analysis from molecular and cellular pathways to neural networks, and from behavior to functional outcomes. These domains span temporal scales that vary from milliseconds to years. Acute assessment of clinical TBI is shifting from reliance on crude categorization of 'mild', 'moderate', and 'severe' TBI to a more nuanced multimodal classification that integrates Clinical assessments, Biomarkers, Imaging, and injury Modifiers (CBI-M) into a single framework. It is critical that the preclinical field adopts a similar approach for experimental TBI in order to improve preclinical fidelity and translational potential. In preclinical TBI, there are unrealized opportunities to synthesize data from a constellation of early functional scores, biomarkers, imaging, and other features to more accurately determine injury severity. We review historic and ongoing efforts to define injury severity in preclinical TBI and discuss the need for a data-driven integrative injury severity index with an eye toward bench-to-bedside translation.

Keywords

Neurotrauma
TBI characterization
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Introduction

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) has the highest incidence of all neurological diseases, impacting over 50 million people and costing at least \$400B annually worldwide^{1,2}. Critically, there is considerable heterogeneity in clinical TBI including type of injury, location of injury, environmental modifiers and even severity of injury. It is hypothesized that clinical trials have failed because we often lump all TBI patients into a single condition based on an acute assessment of severity³. Common animal models such as controlled cortical impact (CCI), fluid percussion injury (FPI), closed head impact, blast injury and penetrating ballistic models focus on modeling specific aspects of clinical phenotypes. Experimental TBI models enable development and testing of therapeutics targeting specific secondary injury mechanisms and pathological features. Despite these advances and the related contributions of preclinical studies to better clinical management of TBI, translation of neuroprotective pharmacologic therapies from the bench to the bedside has not been successful³⁻⁵. Several key factors likely play a role in the failure to translate, such as laboratory animal and injury model heterogeneity,

inconsistent reporting of key dosing variables (e.g., route and timing of administration, duration of treatment), experimental design variability and validating findings across institutions. Critically, many of the preclinical studies used to justify clinical trials did not investigate whether acute reductions in cellular pathology resulted in long-term behavioral improvements^{6,7}. While there is some consensus on how to address many of these issues, for example standardizing a battery of cellular, anatomical and behavioral outcomes and reporting data in repositories using common data elements (CDE)(LaPlaca Harris et al., in this same issue), one unsolved problem remains how best to characterize injury severity across size and time scales to enable targeted, precision therapeutics and stratified clinical trial enrollment.

Injury severity in animal models has been determined primarily by defining a proxy for the amount of biomechanical work (i.e. transfer of energy by a force acting over a distance) applied to the brain. Biomechanics of injury are typically measured by the injury device, such as weight and distance (e.g., weight drop), atmospheric pressure (e.g., fluid percussion) or depth and velocity (e.g., cortical contusion), and/or the mortality rates associated with that level of biomechanical energy transfer. Recognizing that these measures do not take into account individual subject responses, acute biological responses like reflex to toe pinch and righting reflexes have been incorporated into most preclinical TBI protocols. Assessment of injury severity, therefore, involves not only measuring the initial biomechanical insult but also the resultant pathophysiology, which differs in a complex, non-linear way with the type and degree of physical insult causing a range of associated injury phenotypes⁸. While the multi-dimensionality of TBI as a syndrome is increasingly recognized in clinical work, preclinical studies have yet to parallel this practice. If the injuries we create in the laboratory, and the phenotypes we address with our interventions do not match clinical trial populations, translation is doomed to fail. In the present narrative review, we examine the different ways that the field has assessed injury severity in animal models and discuss their relationship to emerging concepts in clinical literature such as the CBI-M diagnostic framework⁹. A major theme is that injury severity in TBI is multimodal and will require multidimensional data integration to generate an injury severity index that is both exquisitely sensitive to biological mechanisms and informative for bidirectional translation: from bench-to-bedside and back.

Clinical Measures of Injury Severity

Clinical TBI diagnosis typically involves clinical and neurological assessments, with imaging and biomarkers contributing clinical decision support for neurosurgical interventions when available. Monitoring neurological and physiological measures, laboratory vitals, and continuous reassessment is standard practice, underlining the multimodal nature of a heterogeneous and complex condition. In spite of all of these data, historically patients with TBI have typically been assigned an initial injury severity primarily based on their Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) scoring¹⁰. The GCS ranges from 3-15, capturing whether patients open their eyes to light pressure touch, to verbal commands, or spontaneously (visual response, 1-4), whether they verbalize with clarity and orientation (verbal response 1-5), and their motor response to a sensory stimulus (motor response, 1-6). Some versions of the GCS include a pupillary light response which subtracts points for abnormality¹¹. The original intention of the GCS was that it be a practical clinical tool to assess level of consciousness and guide immediate care, not as an enduring

diagnostic label¹⁰. The GCS has commonly been used to trichotomize patients into bins of 'mild', 'moderate', or 'severe' based on initial GCS (3-8, severe; 9-12, moderate; and 13-15, mild). However, this practice has been shown to harm patients by generating inappropriate care pathways and can generate stigma in the medical record that negatively impacts subsequent care, resulting in inappropriate clinical nihilism or accusations of malingering and denial of care by physicians and insurers¹²⁻¹⁴. Moreover, a key contributor to failed clinical trials is the practice of patient selection and inclusion/exclusion criteria according to clinical acute triage tools, rather than matching a drug with a pathological mechanism as is standard in preclinical studies^{1,2,5}.

It is evident that simple classification schemes do not capture clinical heterogeneity and therefore, the National Academies of Sciences Engineering and Medicine (NASEM) and the National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS) have recommended that the field abandon the labels mild, moderate, and severe TBI as they may be both misleading and harmful^{15,16}. A key limitation of solely using the GCS is that it does not inform the clinician or the investigator about the biological mechanism(s) of injury or the TBI endotype, nor clinical trajectory^{17,18}. For this reason, modern precision medicine approaches to TBI have involved seeking FDA biomarker qualification for modern brain imaging and biofluid biomarkers as tools for a more complete picture of injury severity to aid in diagnosis and patient stratification for clinical trials^{19,20}. In recognition of these innovations, the 2024 NINDS TBI Classification and Nomenclature initiative developed a 4-pillar framework consisting of Clinical, Biomarkers, Imaging, and injury Modifiers (CBI-M) to capture TBI severity. The Clinical component includes the full GCS as well as GCS pupillary response subscores²¹. The Biomarker component recommends biofluid assays that have passed FDA biomarker qualification²², and the Imaging component includes CT and MRI modalities that have improved outcome prediction²³. Modifiers include features that influence outcome, such as comorbidities and biopsychosocial factors²⁴. The concept is that the full CBI-M provides a more complete clinical picture of injury severity, and including potential injury mechanisms, than each of the components taken in isolation¹⁶. For example, whereas we historically presented a patient with a GCS of 10 as a moderate TBI at admission, we now would describe this same individual as a GCS score 10 (eyes=2; verbal=3, motor=5), GFAP 1200 pg/mL, with a CT indicating subarachnoid hemorrhage and contusion and additional modifiers including a history of TBI and bipolar disorder¹⁶.

A major open question remains how best to incorporate the four pillars of the CBI-M to yield a comprehensive scoring system for injury severity in the clinic. Ongoing work in this area builds on prior advancements in multivariable prediction tools such the International Mission for Prognosis and Analysis of Clinical Trials (IMPACT) and Corticoid Randomization after Significant Head Injury (CRASH) and prognostic tools²⁵. These logistic regression models improved clinical prediction for the risk of mortality and unfavorable outcome over GCS by combining elements of GCS alongside laboratory bloodwork, imaging features, and modifiers such as age and geographic economic development level as stratifiers. These efforts lay the foundation for emerging CBI-M models now under development by multiple groups. The initial CBI-M framework papers focus on acute/subacute assessment, however future efforts will also encompass later timepoints and outcome metrics.

Over the last decades we have learned that classifying severity based on an acute triage score has contributed to poor long-term prognostication and inadequate inclusion/exclusion criteria for clinical trial design. This has led to calls to develop better ways to assess injury

severity that accommodate the heterogeneous spectrum of clinical manifestation. Therefore it is essential to improving injury classification across post-injury time periods if we hope to improve patient prognosis as well better inform clinical trial design. Therefore, when designing preclinical studies with translation in mind, we should consider assessments of severity that are analogous to the CBI-M in that they capture the multi-modality of the rich outcomes data that can be collected in the minutes, hours and days post-injury. A critical next step in bridging the translational gap is to facilitate a more data-based research approach, where investigators can leverage multidimensional preclinical injury outcomes to better align TBI models with clinical correlates. For the remainder of this review, we will dive into the individual domains of injury severity in preclinical models, discussing strengths and weaknesses as well as opportunities. We conclude with a discussion of early attempts to combine multiple features into a coherent injury severity index that takes full advantage of the rich information that preclinical TBI researchers collect, with the expectation that the field is both prompted and encouraged to define an evidenced-based scoring framework to align with clinical CBI-M and improve preclinical model fidelity.

Preclinical Assessment of Injury Severity

Historically, hypotheses in preclinical TBI research focused largely on what was considered a more severe phenotype. Perhaps because many of these hypotheses were driven by collaborations within the field of neurological surgery, many early experiments focused on interventions that would reduce mortality, reduce cell death, and improve energy utilization to restore homeostasis. In fact, in modern Level 1 trauma centers, patients with TBI-related mortality and severe morbidity represent only a minority of those who are hospitalized²⁶. TRACK-TBI (Transforming Research and Clinical Knowledge in Traumatic Brain Injury), the largest US prospective observation cohort study of TBI multi- Level I trauma center data to-date, has two critical findings that need to be considered when modeling TBI. First, while the majority of patients initially classified as moderate-to-severe do report chronic deficits, a significant number of patients have good outcomes and are able to fully return to work and to live independently. Second, the vast majority (over 85%) of TBIs seen by Level I trauma centers are classified as “mild” by GCS trichomization, yet over 50% of these “mild” patients have persistent, life-altering symptoms^{27,28}. Despite this wide variability in clinical outcome, pre-clinical investigators try to minimize variability in order to find statistical significance and generate publishable findings. Often we will see manuscripts reporting that 100% of severe TBIs result in significant cognitive or motor dysfunction. Perhaps more interesting, there are studies of mild TBI that report that none of the animals have persistent deficits following a single mild TBI^{29–32}, whereas other report that the majority of animals have lasting behavioral changes^{33,34}. These data demonstrate that any preclinical model only models a subset of TBI patients. Moreover, they highlight the critical need to develop an agreed upon framework on how we describe injury severity in animal models if we hope to develop therapies and direct them to the clinical population that is most likely to respond to a specific intervention.

There is not a single universal standard for describing injury severity in preclinical TBI models, however over several decades the experimental literature has echoed the clinical practice of

trichotomizing TBI into ‘mild’, ‘moderate’, and ‘severe’ categories. Commonly used parameters to make this trichotimization include biomechanical parameters of the injury model (e.g. atmospheric pressure, piston velocity; **Fig. 1A**)³⁵, and acute neurological responses (e.g., apnea duration, righting reflex time, fluid biomarkers; **Fig. 1B&C**)³⁶. In some cases, investigators have included additional measurements in the days post-injury to further refine assessment of injury such as physiological measures (e.g., weight loss)³⁷, histological changes (e.g., lesion volume; **Fig. 1D**)³⁸, and neurobehavioral scales such as the neurological severity score (NSS)³⁹. At best, preclinical research studies use only a subset of these measures due to narrowly focused hypothesis testing, cost, and other resource limitations.

Figure 1. Modalities frequently used to estimate injury severity in laboratory models. (A) Injury biomechanics can be directly read out from the most common injury devices including fluid percussion injury (FPI), controlled cortical impact (CCI), closed head impact (CHI), and estimated using high speed videography and sensors in blast modeling devices including shock tubes and open field blast. (B) Acute behavioral assessments used in the field to assess the extent of the initial injury. (C) In recent years, there has been rapid innovation and bilateral translation of biofluid biomarkers from bench-to-bedside-and-back. Panels A-C modified from⁴⁰. (D) Pathoanatomical measures can be measured in vivo using advanced MRI modalities and post-mortem through pathology.

Prediction of mortality and morbidity provides some preclinical-to-clinical alignment. In clinical populations, worse clinical injury burden scores (e.g., by GCS, IMPACT, or CRASH) correlate with higher mortality and morbidity^{25,41}. Analogously, in the lateral FPI TBI model increasing the magnitude of the fluid pulse by adjusting the angle of the pendulum one can generate graded injuries, ranging from no mortality, low mortality, and high (even 100%) mortality. Animals with the most severe lateral FPI as measured by a combination of injury biomechanics and acute physiological responses tend to have the more significant and persistent morbidities⁴². Pathoanatomical studies indicate that mortality following FPI (lateral or central) is often attributable to rupture of the vertebral arteries at the foramen magnum due to a rapid increase in intracranial pressure^{43,44}. In humans, brainstem injury resulting from elevated intracranial pressure is similarly associated with a high risk for mortality⁴⁵. However, important

biomechanical differences between quadrupeds and bipeds limit translatability. Whereas rodents often die from brainstem-related injury at higher levels of biomechanical perturbation, humans may sustain more extensive supratentorial pathology in the absence of overt brainstem lesions, which may or may not lead to death. It should be noted that animals with rapid neurologic or physiologic decline often meet animal welfare endpoint criteria, whereas the foundational clinical principles of beneficence and non-maleficence inherently reduce mortality and morbidities for a given TBI severity, skewing true comparison of severe TBI between preclinical and clinical scenarios. Most TBIs presenting to level 1 trauma centers are classified as 'mild', yet many still suffer persistent symptoms including pain to neurocognitive problems, to impulse control, personality and mood disorders^{27,28}. The pathologies of this large swath of "mild" patients are not easily aligned to animals using crude, binary outcomes such as presence of mortality and morbidity.

Injury Devices, Biomechanics, and Sensors Measuring Injury Severity

In comparing across preclinical models, it has been proposed that levels of mortality be binned by injury parameters (i.e. atmospheric pressure, piston speed, etc.) in order to categorize animals as receiving a "mild", "moderate", or "severe" TBI⁴⁶. For discovery purposes, one great advantage of preclinical models over clinical research is that experimenters control the initial injury and have the capacity to measure it. CCI was originally developed at General Motors to attempt measuring the mechanical compliance of brain tissue for refinement of the Head Injury Criterion (HIC) for automotive safety⁴⁷. Later, when CCI devices were refined to study biological aspects of TBI, accelerometers or linear displacement contact sensors were attached to the impact tip to measure motion of the impactor or head⁴⁸. Some CCI devices have load sensors to measure impact energy in dynes. FPI models typically use pressure sensors to measure the pressure of the fluid pulse (saline) immediately before it impacts the exposed dura mater to the intracranial space. Injury severity is typically associated with the peak pressure reported in atmospheres, however technical issues may impact the accuracy of this measurement⁴⁹. A relatively recent update to the impact-acceleration model⁵⁰, is the Closed-Head Impact Model of Engineered Rotational Acceleration (CHIMERA), which produces a rapid angular velocity after a closed head lateral impact with energy reported as energy in joules⁵¹. Several other closed head injury models exist, applying a single or repetitive blunt force to the head or skull, including repurposed CCI devices with modifications to the piston and weight drop (WD)⁵². Blast injury models include open field blast and shock/blast tube configuration that measure blast overpressure amplitude and duration at different locations, including adjacent to the animal (see Johnson et al. in this same issue). The penetrating ballistic-like brain injury (PBBi) models direct mechanical displacement by projectile and defines injury biomechanics through controlled probe trajectory, penetration depth, and rapid balloon inflation to a specified fraction of brain volume, producing a reproducible transient cavity that drives tissue deformation^{53,54}. Adding to the biomechanical heterogeneity across models and studies is the age and size of the animal (e.g., juvenile versus adult animals, male versus female, mouse versus rat versus porcine), which will lead to varying deficits and pathology for the same biomechanical insult.

In addition to measuring injury device parameters as described above, high speed cineradiographic and videography has been used to measure head kinematics and validate

sensor information in several preclinical TBI models^{55,56}. Despite these efforts in rodents, the biomechanical details of clinical TBI are rarely known, which is an inherent limitation of linking severity or function to the biomechanical inputs (at all temporal and spatial scales). In attempts to find realistic loading parameters, human TBI has been simulated using cadavers, anthropomorphic models, and computer simulation to obtain realistic kinematics and estimate tissue stresses and strains⁵⁷. Compounding the issues of unknown loading conditions and nonlinear scaling, biomechanical simulations of human TBI have not been universally used to define loading parameters for preclinical models, with the exception of some large animal models^{55,56}. Therefore, translational validity relies the available parameters already collected (as described above) so that we best align injury biomechanics with clinical TBI, albeit with some degree of error⁵⁸.

Despite the advantage of controllability in experimental TBI models, most clinical TBIs involve a combination of physical insults that are difficult to describe biomechanically (e.g., a car accident may result in both blunt force impact and acceleration/deceleration injury) and polytrauma involving extremity fractures, internal organ damage, blood loss and other insults can confound prognosis. Is a severe, or for that matter a mild, TBI determined solely by energy transferred to the brain, or is it complicated by additional factors that may include pre-injury nutrition, sleep quality, substance abuse, etc or the presence of a second insult, whether neurological (i.e. hypoxia, ischemia, seizure) or peripheral (i.e. broken bone, cardiovascular or pulmonary insult)? This must be kept in mind when trying to assess how biomechanical inputs in experimental models align with injury severity in the clinical scenario. While daunting to consider, and while pre-clinical researchers are limited in the parameters they can compare, an injury severity index combined with analytic tools offers excellent opportunities to incorporate multiple pieces of information related to the injury that go far beyond device settings, and will allow us to close gaps between the clinical population and preclinical models.

In fact, the recent proliferation of models and researchers and renewed efforts to improve clinical translation has prompted PRECISE-TBI to focus on cataloging TBI models (see Surles-Zeigler et al. in this same special issue; RRID:SCR_024626) and facilitating data pooling for correlating biomechanical *input* and functional/pathologic *output*. While computational and physical modeling can only *approximate* the energy that is transduced to the brain and the resulting tissue stress and strain, these approaches have been valuable in establishing injury tolerances and guiding preclinical TBI studies. For example, studies using biofidelic modeling of forces moving through the viscoelastic medium of brain tissue have suggested profound differences in the stresses and strains on lissencephalic brains of rodents versus gyrencephalic brains of humans⁵⁹. For this reason, there have been efforts over the years to use gyrencephalic species such as ferrets and pigs⁶⁰. However, at the current time, the vast majority of preclinical TBI research occurs in lissencephalic species such as mice and rats. For this reason, researchers have relied largely on comparative pathoanatomical features of injuries to assess the translational impact of laboratory injury devices. There are many ways one could approach developing a more unified framework for preclinical injury severity. However, we propose that, to make this tool more clinically relevant, we start using a recent framework for improved description of clinical TBI. As such, in the following sections we will demonstrate how we can frame many of the preclinical measures of outcome that are available to researchers in the context of the CBI-M and, in doing so, highlight the similarities, the stark and obvious

differences, and identify areas for consideration in developing an injury severity index for experimental TBI.

Physiological and Neurological Description of Injury Severity (“Clinical” to Preclinical)

Typical clinical measures of injury include the GSC (including pupillary response), physiological vitals (e.g., hemodynamics, oxygenation, temperature), standard blood lab workup (including coagulation status and blood gases), in addition to neuroimaging and intracranial pressure sensing, as appropriate. However, similar multi-monitoring assessments are rarely done following experimental TBI, with the exception of physiologic monitoring in large animal models^{61–63}, and a small number of specialized studies in rodents^{64,65}. However, in some cases the animal care records may contain anesthesia monitoring including pulse oxygenation devices to measure heartrate, and tissue oxygenation, respiration assessments, and blood pressure monitoring. In the other areas of neurotrauma such as spinal cord injury, these intraoperative care measures have been found to be strong translational predictors of neurorecovery in both rodents and humans^{66–68}.

While not typically considered in the clinical framework, measures of neurological function acutely following TBI also can offer accurate and sensitive readouts of injury severity (**Fig.1B**). The most appropriate behavioral task to gauge injury severity depends on the model used, as each model is known to affect different neurobehavioral systems. Whether it is a reflex, cognitive, neurological, vestibular, or sensorimotor task, these preclinical measures (and their clinical analogues) can provide early functional indications of injury severity. There are many reflexes that have been measured in the seconds to minutes following injury including eye-blink, toe pinch paw withdrawal, and righting reflex. Some might argue that apnea duration, the loss and subsequent recover of spontaneous breathing, could be considered a reflex. In fact, the righting reflex latency is one of the most often used neurological measures of injury severity, and has been suggested as an experimental analogue to human loss of consciousness⁶⁹. Following TBI, the time to right is longer relative to an anesthesia control, and with higher magnitude of biomechanical force (i.e. atmospheres, piston speed) corresponding with a longer recovery time. This latency is a predictor of later outcomes including lesion size, extent of tissue deformation, and chronic cognitive impairment^{36,69}. Due to its association with multiple modes of dysfunction, righting reflex latency is used across all major TBI models, including CCI, FPI, and CHIMERA⁶⁹.

To more closely mirror a clinical neurological battery such as the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS), researchers also use the Neurological Severity Score (NSS). The NSS is a measure that is comprised of a series of tasks designed to test gait, reflexes, seeking behavior, and balance³⁹. Despite widespread use, recent work has challenged the efficacy of these early behavioral measures to accurately predict long-term outcomes⁷⁰. In fact, there is discordance among studies comparing tissue response to behavioral outcome, with some studies showing poor correlation^{70,71} and others documenting positive correlation⁷². Whether the incidence of conflicting reports is more pronounced for specific injury severity classifications (i.e., studies claiming “mild” experimental TBI vs “severe”), individual TBI models (e.g., weight drop vs CCI), or singular behavioral assays (e.g., righting reflex vs NSS) is difficult to discern from the current

literature due to many studies limiting their reporting of these assays to methods sections rather than displaying individual subject-level data.

Other behavioral tasks captured in the sub-acute recovery period can also be considered measures of clinical outcome as they correspond more to the initial response to injury. For example, measuring sensorimotor/vestibular deficits in the first days following injury, such as the rotarod and beam walk tests have been used to predict long-term outcomes.⁷³ Cognitive function can be tested acutely after experimental TBI and used as a prognostic tool for long-term outcomes as well. However, while tests such as the Novel Object Recognition (NOR) or fear conditioning protocols can give early indication of injury severity⁸, these tasks are often reserved for used as long-term outcome measures of recovery from injury rather than initial injury severity markers due to confounders such as anesthesia-related impacts on cognition and prominent motor deficits being common in the immediate days following rodent TBI.

Finally, there may be missed opportunities in the data we choose to collect, or perhaps choose not to collect, after experimental injury. Many investigators would tell you that an animal may seize immediately following injury, even though others that receive a similar injury do not. Others will highlight that some acute behaviors are observed in rodents and humans but have yet to gain widespread adoption in the reporting protocols. One example is the fencing response or the tonic posturing characterized by *the extension and flexion of opposite arms*⁷⁴. Fencing response can be an indicator of the mechanical force magnitude (injury severity) to the midbrain. Similarly, intracranial pressure is commonly measured clinically as the dura and underlying brain swell into a craniotomy, but it is rarely measured in preclinical models. Finally, some animals will develop pulmonary edema, evidenced by raspy breathing, whereas others do not⁷⁵. Many of these potentially important variables have not been systematically recorded in the field. Measures such as toe pinch and righting reflex have likely been widely adopted because they are easy to assess and come free of charge. And while measures of intracranial or mean arterial blood pressure would certainly improve all studies, there can be constraints, whether financial or in study design, that limit the use of these critical clinical variables. However, some opportunities have been missed because, in years past, sample sizes were too small to account for all of the potential points of variance. In other words, it is easy to do a univariate comparison between righting-reflex and outcome. Moreover, it is likely that one lab can compare their righting reflex measures to those of other labs to try to align injury severity. However, as we transition into the era of data sharing, there are now opportunities to combine observations from many small studies, and perhaps accumulate sufficient sample size to determine whether any one of these, or perhaps none at all, are critical preclinical variables that the field should adopt as standard endpoints. Accumulating evidence suggests that preclinical TBI models may suffer from a similar classification problem as clinical TBI⁷⁰. As the clinical world shifts from a high reliance on GCS to the multimodal CBI-M model, there may similarly be an opportunity to recontextualize preclinical functional/behavioral tasks as one-in-a-constellation of early measures to more accurately determine injury severity.

Biofluid Biomarker Description of Injury Severity (Biomarkers)

While behavioral tasks rely on neurocognitive homology to draw clinically meaningful inferences, biofluid biomarkers assayed from accessible biofluid sources such as blood are often more directly translatable between animal and clinical studies⁷⁶(**Fig.1C**). In searching for sensitive and specific indicators of injury severity, a core panel of biofluid biomarkers including glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), ubiquitin C-terminal hydrolase L1 (UCH-L1), neurofilament light chain (NfL), tau and phosphorylated tau (tau/p-tau), microtubule-associated protein 2 (MAP-2), and S100 calcium-binding protein B (S100B) may reliably anchor cross-species alignment⁷⁶⁻⁷⁹. Further, with well-characterized kinetics that index hyperacute and evolving injury, biofluid biomarkers have the potential to deepen our mechanistic understanding across preclinical TBI subtypes within a multimodal, CBI-M-like framework and improve hypothesis-generating guidance for therapy development and. lead to better patient stratification for in future clinical trials^{80,81}.

UCH-L1 provides a clear preclinical-to-clinical discovery arc as it was first highlighted in the laboratory setting as a candidate biomarker using proteomics following rodent CCI⁸² and fluid percussion⁸³. Subsequent characterization using CCI demonstrated that UCH-L1 levels rise in both CSF and serum following injury⁸⁴. These patterns were later validated in human biofluids and have since become one of the first FDA-qualified biomarkers incorporated alongside other biomarkers into clinical testing^{80,85,86}. In contrast, GFAP, S100B, NfL, and tau/p-tau emerged through bidirectional work across the pre-clinical and clinical realms which typically combined knowledge regarding the biological role of proteins gained from animal studies with the identification of the same proteins in human TBI cohorts^{77,87-90}. Following identification in humans, animal models of TBI proved to be essential for determining candidate biomarker kinetics, dose-responses, and detailing cell-specific patho-mechanisms. Cross-walking the pre-clinical and clinical settings in this way allowed for the mechanistic contextualization of many of the blood-based biomarkers currently used in the clinic⁵¹. This history underscores the importance of bidirectional clinical and preclinical alignment of biofluid biomarkers in such a way that injury severity can be more accurately described both within and across species.

A recent systematic review explicitly operationalizes this alignment strategy by screening for pre-clinical studies measuring many of the core candidate panel of biomarkers and highlighting their clinically-actionable insights⁹¹. Across pre-clinical studies and models of TBI, all markers were found to increase with injury severity with individual biomarkers exhibiting distinct temporal profiles⁹²⁻⁹⁴. Multiple large, prospective clinical cohorts mirror these pre-clinical observations. In TRACK-TBI, day-of-injury GFAP and UCH-L1 levels demonstrate substantial prognostic value for death and unfavorable outcome 6-months post-injury⁸⁰. In an independent study, plasma GFAP, UCH-L1 and MAP-2 were found to be diagnostically informative for acute outcomes including death, neurosurgical intervention, and prolonged mechanical ventilation within 30-60 minutes of the injury occurring⁷⁸. Further, serial sampling consistently supports the use of biomarkers such as GFAP and NfL for patient monitoring and potential pharmacodynamic readouts concretely defining human sampling windows that preclinical studies can emulate^{52,56,68}. The reliable testing of biofluid biomarkers in both the laboratory and at the bedside alongside the cross-species conservation of kinetics and pharmacodynamic responses positions this approach as an invaluable component for consistently defining injury severity and better addressing the translatability crisis currently plaguing the TBI field. Perhaps the current challenge is that, while access to blood and CSF is relatively easy in animals, and

can be sampled with minimal additional cost, a current technological barrier exists. There is a clear unmet need to develop an affordable technology, even if just an easy to use and affordable ELISA kit, that would allow for rapid (for acute drug studies) and longitudinal (outcome or delayed therapy) evaluation of blood-based biomarkers in every neurotrauma lab.

Pathoanatomical Description of Injury Severity (Imaging and Histopathology)

The well-worn adage “seeing is believing” is especially appropriate to neuroimaging research as one approach to describing the type and structural extent of injury, thus providing a window into assessing severity of injury (**Fig.1D**). The imaging pillar of the new CBI-M framework for classifying clinical TBI constrains the use of mostly computed tomography (CT) imaging for acute analysis of structural injury severity, with MRI being employed only for acute pediatric cases not appropriate for radiation exposure, and for post-acute and chronic phases after TBI⁹⁵. The CBI-M framework makes clear that the four major gross structural findings of: subarachnoid hemorrhage, skull fractures, contusion and acute sub-dural hematomas, along with the imaging findings of: epidural /intraventricular/intracerebral hematomas and traumatic axonal or microvascular injury underpin the majority of cases⁹⁶. While there are no recommendations for the best imaging method, the new initiative makes clear that the lesion size, number, location and type of structural finding are important considerations when assessing severity via imaging. Devising imaging feature clusters that inform on injury severity and the prognostic and therapeutic implications remain an urgent clinical research goal and a few landmark papers have examined this in large prospective clinical cohorts⁹⁷.

Within the preclinical neuroimaging arena, frequent and acute phase use of MRI can provide an unbiased, whole brain analysis of injury type, location, and extent of damage. In parallel to the clinical CBI-M guidelines, preclinical MRI sequences are available to measure the mass effect of large lesions, the accumulation of tissue edema, and the locational relevance of hematomas. The uptake of preclinical MRI may well increase in future to aid in the diagnostic classification and prognosis of injury severity, as adoption of standardized analytical pipelines increases^{98,99}, similar to the clinical arena where it is common practice^{100–103}. While traumatic axonal or microvascular injury are easily accessible features from TBI research subjects derived using diffusion and susceptibility-weighted imaging, their implementation at the equivalent spatial and temporal resolution in the rodent or ferret brain is not as readily attainable as it is on standard clinical research spectrometers¹⁰⁴. The major reason for this is that, despite using the highest performance gradient hardware, achieving equivalent signal-to-noise for preclinical-sized brain voxels requires far more time per subject than a typical clinical scan. Other factors, such as the limited number of signal acquisition channels available to capture image information using preclinically radiofrequency coils, largely due to their small size, decreases signal-to-noise, increasing sample times and preventing the high throughput of subjects in the scanner. Finally, while the frontal, maxillary and sphenoid sinuses contribute to image distortion effects that may obscure the delineation of common injuries to that region of brain in clinical imaging, the problem in the rodent is far worse, not only due to the large size ratio of the air-filled ear canals-to-brain, but the out-sized impact of the signal susceptibility effect of even small amounts of blood on adjacent brain regions within such a small brain. Additionally, feasibility constraints are prominent for neuroimaging in pre-clinical TBI, as not every institution, or perhaps laboratory

within an institution, have access to in vivo imaging. Or, in many cases, while imaging is available, scanners are located remotely from the lab and with potential issues related to scheduling a well-used campus resource with precisely-timed TBI.

Histopathology represents the classic tool to describe TBI severity from a pathoanatomical perspective (**Fig.1D**). Although clinical histopathology is limited to biopsy samples and post-mortem analysis, preclinical studies often involve planned, whole-brain tissue collection from a subset of subjects for histopathological and immunohistochemical analysis at acute timepoints. While there are known tissue preparation artifacts, histological staining can indicate edema, bleeding, non-specific cell loss, and regional patterns of damage. Common gross neuropathological measures in the field include lesion size and atrophy of key brain regions such as the cortex, hippocampus, and thalamus. These measurements highlight substantial injury model-dependent differences in broad tissue response with open skull CCI injury being characterized by frank contusion at the impact site, whereas some models (e.g., FPI) produce more diffuse changes throughout the brain. At the cellular level, the gold standard for obtaining cell phenotypic information following experimental TBI is immunohistochemistry. This approach has been critical in identifying hundreds of molecular and cell changes, including cytoskeletal and axonal alterations¹⁰⁵, astrocyte and microglial reactivity and other neuroinflammation indicators¹⁰⁶, free radical and oxidative damage¹⁰⁷, mitochondrial dysfunction¹⁰⁸, and many other markers of cell signaling and structural abnormalities. Many TBI models have particularly specific cell damage signatures, such as hippocampal cell loss following FPI and axonal damage markers in rotational injury models¹⁰⁹. Newer technologies such as spatial transcriptomics are beginning to transform our understanding of tissue pathology by providing an information rich picture of pathological molecular signatures after injury in preclinical models¹¹⁰ that may lead to future RNA based biomarkers in humans, especially as we come to understand the alignment of tissue and blood transcriptomics¹¹¹.

Importantly, preclinical injury models allow for readily and robustly accessible repeated measures (neuroimaging) or serial (histological) assessment of neuroanatomy following TBI. These data allow preclinical researchers to capture a temporally dense, longitudinal time-course of the injury phase that benefits both the study of structural and functional pathomechanisms, as well as informs the most useful features of the acute phase that are predictive of outcome. Combining data from these imaging modalities with biofluid analysis of protein biomarkers, as indicated by the CBI-M framework, better positions experimental models of TBI to provide unrivalled insight into mechanism, and ultimately provides parallel preclinical pillars for a severity index. A multitude of these types of multi-modal preclinical, biomarker, and imaging data have in fact already been collected by the preclinical Operation Brain Trauma Therapy (OBTT) and Translational Project in Neurotrauma (TOP-NT) Consortia^{112,113}. OBTT has published a series of manuscripts describing their findings that integrate multiple species, injury models, and modalities of endpoint metrics. Further, the first overview of TOPNT's data integration pipelines have been recently published^{114,115}, as well as the first imaging results¹¹⁶. These types of preclinical data may easily translate to the clinic and sidestep the many complexities and logistical issues of obtaining the same detailed data in acute brain injury patients, providing an opportunity to develop and refine analytic workflows on a severity index that may later be tested clinically.

Other Laboratory Factors that Influence Injury Severity (Modifiers)

The last pillar of the clinical CBI-M framework is “modifiers”. Clinical modifiers include a range of additional factors that may impact injury prognosis and clinical trajectory such as biopsychosocial determinates of health, and pre-existing health conditions¹¹⁷. Many clinical modifiers may not have clear equivalents in the pre-clinical realm. However, some factors such as extracranial injuries or biological sex may translate. Factors beyond force applied to the brain, fluid-based biomarkers, or neuroimaging should be considered as potential modifiers in the laboratory setting. Below we highlight modifiers that may impact our assessment of injury severity in the laboratory. These key factors are likely to have contributed to multiple failed translation and clinical trials^{2,5}.

Uncontrolled Variance

A major roadblock encountered in the development and implementation of TBI models is uncontrolled variance, even with controlled input parameters. Between animal variance in both the initial injuries and in long-term outcomes complicates interpretation of injury severity, limits stratification for targeted therapeutic testing, and hampers alignment to human TBI. Variance can be observed both within a laboratory and between laboratories. As highlighted above, many investigators report severity based specifically on the device parameters (e.g., atmospheric pressure of a fluid pulse, velocity of a moving piston. While the data likely will be parametric over a large group of animals, with the majority of data points clustering around a mean and with relatively low variance, there certainly are animals that exhibit a different response than the majority to similar injury parameters. Do we consider these animals to have the same injury severity because of the settings on our device? Or should we incorporate a variety of post-injury measurements such as return of spontaneous breathing, eye blink, toe pinch, righting reflexes, and/or the recovery of weight over time as proxies for severity? Can we even determine which animal falls on the mild end of the spectrum as compared to a severe injury before we have some measurement of brain pathology (i.e. MRI or histochemistry) or behavioral dysfunction? Yet, most of our preclinical studies assign severity at the time of injury based on the output of the device, not the response of the subject, even in cases where early behavioral metrics that may more closely align to clinical practice are measured.

Additionally, variance between experimenters is observed within a lab. Two individuals using animals from an identical source (e.g., vivarium and delivery) can use the same injury device and parameters and have different outcomes. Yet, their recorded severity measures would be the same. Therefore, we argue that recording surgeon for each experiment is a critical CDE. These inconsistencies are likely due to the many opportunities to introduce small amounts of variance (i.e., is the position of impact truly identical, is the seal of the fluid percussion cap the same, how reproducible is the zero point before CCI?). While most labs specifically train individuals until their results fall within a certain range of outcomes, this inter-experimenter variability is infrequently controlled for after training or reported in disseminated results.

Perhaps the greatest source of preclinical variance, however, occurs at the inter-laboratory level. Within a single TBI model, even when using a similar device (e.g., make,

manufacturer, parameters), outcomes vary substantially between labs. However, in the absence of planned multi-center preclinical studies, it is often difficult to directly measure and correct for cross-center variance. There are increasing opportunities to explicitly examine cross-laboratory effects using pooled retrospective analysis of publicly shared datasets deposited in community repositories such as the Open Data Commons for TBI (odc-tbi.org) (see Martone et al., in this same issue). A few papers have performed this type of analysis and have successfully been able to discern consistent biomarker signatures across multiple laboratories by over-powering cross-laboratory variance with very large pooled sample sizes^{112,118,119}. However, in these types of studies, variance due to center is confounded with other, poorly specified sources of variance such as biomarker platform used, rodent strain, injury device parameters, university-specific animal care standards, among enumerable others. These unspecified sources of variance accumulate as an increase in overall error. One recent preclinical study the TOP-NT consortium was designed explicitly to examine cross-center effects by performing multicenter analysis of the same biomarkers using the same platforms¹¹². This allows us to quantify and measure the impact of center on biomarker assessments. This will be a topic of a series of papers from TOP-NT in the near future.

Another source of variance is the specific design of the injury device used. Many companies manufacture different CCI devices. For this reason, PRECISE-TBI has developed a model catalog resource that provides research resource identifiers for specific CCI devices (see Surles-Zeigler in this same issue). An additional complexity results from the existence of a variety of CCI impact tips that differ not only by size and material properties, but also shape of the tip that impacts the brain. Also, few labs use the same coordinates for the impact, with differences on the rostral/caudal or medial/lateral axes. Further, in the last decade, one of the fastest growing models, regardless of device, is repetitive brain injury. This adds another layer of complexity to harmonizing across studies given the potentially exponential influence of injury parameter differences in a design with repeated insults. On one hand, this is perhaps an advantage, as this adds heterogeneity across the field that better mirrors the clinical population. However, how can one determine whether the severity of injury in one lab corresponds to a similar severity in any other based solely on biomechanical inputs recorded at the level of the device? Any injury severity index would need to directly address these sources of variability and try to account for them in analytic workflows.

Collectively, these challenges highlight that there are critical factors (or modifiers) related to the injury device and who is creating the injury that will necessarily impact injury outcome, regardless of the injury settings on any given device. The need for harmonization strategies that move beyond nominal injury parameters and instead account for laboratory- and protocol-specific effects while anchoring injury severity to shared phenotypic or biological readouts (i.e., CBI-M aligned). From an analytic perspective, these sources of heterogeneity argue for treating laboratory, device, and protocol differences as structured contributors to variance rather than unmodeled noise. When harmonizing data across studies, approaches that explicitly account for center-level effects, align injury severity based on more detailed readouts, and evaluate robustness across laboratories may provide a more stable framework than relying on set injury-device parameters alone. Such strategies are increasingly feasible as community repositories and multi-center initiatives enable pooled analyses and retrospective comparisons across diverse experimental designs.

Timing of injury severity assessments

Timing of injury severity assessments determines whether they reflect the level of ‘exposure’ to the initial forces that impacted the brain or the initiation and impact of secondary, cascading pathomechanisms that follow the primary injury and evolve over time. For this reason, it may be useful to think of the initial exposure as the only true ‘cause’ and everything that follows as a ‘risk/outcome’ of this exposure. Based on our experience with multi-center studies, this view seems to be somewhat uncommon, with researchers often conflating acute outcomes with injury severity (see Figure 1). Technically, metrics such as clinical/preclinical neurobehavioral symptoms, biomarker changes, and imaging all reflect hyperacute outcomes that follow the initial exposure. Since biological systems involve complex feedback loops, it can be very difficult to disentangle initial injury exposure (i.e., biomechanical insult applied to the brain) from the outputs of regulated biological processes. For example, secondary cell death, inflammation, homeostatic mechanisms, repair pathways, and neuroplasticity are all triggered by the initial TBI event. The further a subject is from the initial event, the more these secondary injury processes start to take over. The rate and extent of damage caused by these cascading, biologically-regulated pathways is a large source of between subject variance in the form of “injury-response”, often impacting researchers’ perception of initial injury severity. For example, just because two people fell from their roof and had a frontal TBI does not mean we should immediately collapse them into the same injury group. We would want to look at measures including blood-based biomarkers, imaging and perhaps acute recovery before we providing a prognosis or developing a treatment plan. Following this logic, why would we determine whether to administer an animal a drug, or pseudo-randomize or treatment groups based on the most acute measures alone? If a therapy is administered to an animal at 6 or even 24 hours, shouldn’t we consider as many dimensions as possible to best predict which animals are likely to develop persistent deficits opposed to those that might spontaneously recover?

Defining injury severity is further complicated by the need to align with the clinical setting where, for feasibility constraints described previously, the exact details of the biomechanical insult experienced by the brain are often unknown necessitating the use of hyperacute physiological, imaging, or biomarker readouts as practical proxies for injury severity. In this context, combining information about initial experimental exposure with hyperacute response measures may provide a more translationally relevant framework for characterizing injury severity across preclinical and clinical studies. In summary, one of the major unresolved problems in assessing TBI for translational research is demarcating injury severity from injury response and understanding how the hyperacute behavioral variables, while technically capturing early portions of injury response, can be denoted as reflecting clinically-relevant injury severity metrics and how these variables may evolve with time.

An increasingly discussed implication of this framework is that TBI may give rise to multiple biological endotypes, in which subjects exposed to seemingly identical initial insults nonetheless diverge in pathology and recovery trajectories due to latent, time-dependent processes that are not directly observable at the time of injury. Importantly, such divergence may reflect either genuinely distinct biological programs or the influence of unmeasured injury modifiers and resilience factors that shape injury response over time. From this perspective,

injury severity may be better represented not as a single, ordinal-categorical variable (i.e., mild, moderate, severe) but as a family of related injury states that reflect distinct patterns of early injury response. Analytically, this motivates approaches that emphasize data-driven stratification, multivariate profiling, and longitudinal characterization of subjects to identify coherent subgroups with shared response trajectories. This approach would thereby enable early inference regarding the likelihood of divergent long-term outcomes among subjects with superficially similar injuries based on hyperacute response measures, rather than relying solely on nominal injury parameters or single early outcome measures. In fact some would argue that, this is an ideal example of a bedside-to-bench and back-again opportunity. While this need was determined based on clinical outcomes, controlled rodent studies provide an incredible window to test a range of hypotheses. Findings from these pre-clinical studies could then be used to optimize clinical prognostic models.

Misalignments to Clinical

Another modifier, and one that is perhaps more in common between rodent and human studies is that acute care varies between laboratories as it might between clinical practices. For example, patients with more severe injuries are often admitted to the neurointensive care unit (neuro ICU) and continually assessed with intracranial pressure (ICP) monitors, repeated neuroimaging (e.g., head computed tomography [hCT]), and serial blood draws. Clinical variables derived from these standard care procedures such as ICP, evolving hCT findings (e.g., midline shift, compression of basal cisterns, epidural hematoma, intraventricular/subarachnoid hemorrhage, etc), and the trajectory of routine blood-based measures of metabolic, inflammatory, and coagulation status are routinely integrated into clinical decision making^{120–123}. In contrast, this depth and frequency of monitoring during the acute post-injury phase is rarely mirrored in preclinical TBI studies, where many of these routinely collected clinical variables are either not measured or only captured at isolated timepoints. This can be further complicated as there is variance between standards between institutions, and individual animal management between labs. For example, many institutions require the application of post-injury pain medication. This may include anti-inflammatory compounds such as Carprofen. It can also include treatment with opiate analogues such as Buprenorphine. Other labs do not have to apply pain medication. Some labs will provide extensive rehydration, injecting multiple milliliters of saline or lactated ringers daily. Other labs provide no additional hydration. These are just two examples of post-TBI recovery management that vary significantly between labs. However, when analyzing data, these variables are rarely considered when examining the relationship between injury biomechanics and outcome. It is clear, therefore, that tracking each post-recovery variable is critical when trying to develop a framework that predicts which rats will develop lasting phenotypes and perhaps how to best translate a finding from the bench to the bedside.

Collectively, these misalignments highlight the need for a bidirectional translational framework in which preclinical injury severity and early response measures are informed by the clinical variables most relevant to decision making and long-term patient outcomes, while remaining grounded in what is experimentally feasible. In this context, blood-based biomarkers with demonstrated cross-species relevance and established clinical utility (e.g., GFAP, UCH-L1)

may serve as a pragmatic starting point for improving alignment between preclinical models and clinical assessment frameworks, and represent a shared opportunity for both preclinical studies and future clinical workflows to incorporate the serial measurement of biologically informative injury signals¹²⁴. And, while neuroimaging may not be feasible in every subject, when possible, validating biomechanical and blood-based biomarker findings with limited imaging data can allow investigators to improve their categorization of injury severity based on biomechanics and righting time, to include correlative data related to acute cell death and neuroanatomical changes. To this end, we call upon basic scientists to initiate greater collaboration with clinicians to better inform the selection, timing, and interpretation of hyperacute and subacute outcome measures in a way that prioritizes shared constructs of injury severity and improves harmonization across experimental and clinical TBI research.

Variability in species and outcome measures

While it is typically reported which species is used, and most commonly strain is reported as well, it is well-accepted that differences in the background of animals can play a critical role on outcomes. Whether it has to do with subtle differences in genetics, animal size, quality of the visual system (albino as opposed to pigmented eyes) or any number of other species-related variables. Therefore, it is critical not only to report species and strain but also to consider whether studies need to be replicated across species – and specifically into larger animal models before translation.

In addition, outcome measures can very easily modify our interpretation of our injury. For example behavioral and neurocognitive sequelae affecting the majority of TBI patients (approximately 85% with Glasgow Coma Scale scores of 13–15), such as executive function deficits (e.g., impulse control, working memory, and cognitive flexibility), mood disturbances (e.g., new-onset depression or anxiety), and chronic pain syndromes (e.g., post-traumatic headache), remain challenging, though not impossible, to assess in animal models^{125,126}. As a result, commonly used preclinical outcome measures may insufficiently capture the domains most relevant to patient-reported chronic morbidity following mild TBI despite the significant influence these morbidities have on quality of life.

Labs may not run a complete behavioral battery that includes the majority of outcomes related to motor, learning, executive function, or sleep. However, how do you know if your animal is truly 'mild' and lacks a more severe phenotype if you only test one outcome? Conversely, how can you be convinced that you have a severe chronic phenotype if you haven't evaluated multiple other behaviors to determine whether the effect is widespread? These are issues that cannot be easily addressed at the individual laboratory level and require the accumulation of 1000s of data points across multiple labs doing a range of behavioral tests. As with the other variables discussed above, if we do not consider, record and add these outcome data to our injury severity framework, we are limiting our ability to select the best model to test a given TBI phenotype. Ultimately, this undermines development therapeutic screens that translate into successful clinical trials.

Overcoming Challenges through Integrative Data-Driven Approaches

As we have highlighted, one of the key challenges of assigning an injury severity index in humans or animals is defining the variables that best capture the full syndrome of TBI. TBI is a highly multidimensional disorder impacting multiple brain systems with distributed effects throughout the neuroaxis. The consequence is a complex syndrome of effects on diverse endpoints including consciousness, mood, neurocognition and sensorimotor effects, each with their own variance and timing features. Arguably, TBI is not sufficiently captured by any one injury parameter. Moreover, injury related variables do not exist in isolation. For example, one-way ANOVAs are great at comparing one acute physiological measure (i.e. piston velocity, atmospheres of pressure or righting reflex) to an outcome (i.e. cognitive performance). However, these univariate analyses will necessarily fail to capture the complexity of the disorder. Is it feasible to determine cause-and-effect, for example, if you are only looking at a blood-based biomarker, the change in a receptor protein or diffuse axonal injury in fixed tissue, when that variable is looked at in isolation? Instead, it is useful to frame TBI as a complex constellation of disease features. Mathematically, a composite injury severity index can be constructed from a weighted combination of several measures into a single index. For example, injury severity could be represented by developing a single score that combines the biomechanics of injury (e.g. impact force), the extent of tissue damage (e.g. MRI measures), initial neurological assessments (e.g. righting score), and biofluid biomarkers. This framing is consistent with the CBI-M model that is being advanced by the clinical TBI field^{9,127}. Even if lab resources are limited, there is opportunity for everyone to improve the richness of their acute data collection. Moreover, if there is a clear pre-clinical need that is demonstrated for an entire field (as opposed to a single lab), this may stimulate a vendor(s) to develop easy-to-implement tools (i.e. a cost-effective lab-bench side tool for measurement of fluid-based biomarkers).

The key to this approach, while managing the issue of variance, is to convert the univariate variables to a common scale. Correlation may be a well-suited for this application as it emphasizes shared variance across variables, converting them to a modified z-score, the Pearson correlation coefficient or non-linear equivalents. One approach to addressing many of the difficulties described at length is to first map the *intercorrelations* of multiple measures including the injury severity generated at the level of the device (i.e. depth/acceleration for CCI, atmospheric pressure and/or angle for FPI or height/weight for impact acceleration), the hyperacute response measured by neuroimaging or histological approaches (i.e. cell death or neuroinflammation markers), biofluid biomarkers, and early behavior (**Fig.2**). The challenge is to break down silos so that researchers no longer continue to define their severity by univariate measures such as the measurement of impact parameters from the injury device, which ignores pathology, or scale their severity based on neurological outcome, which ignores biomarker information. The animals that had the most cell death and worst behavior, and highest biomarker and imaging pathology are determined to be the most severe, while those with minimal cell death and behavioral dysfunction have lower injury severity scores (**Fig.2A**). Such an approach to creating an injury severity index would capture the full information provided by the common measures of severity used by the field to describe the 'syndromic space' of TBI¹²⁸. A syndromic injury severity index score could then be used in second order analyses such as structured causal modeling approaches to help disentangle the impact of therapeutics from the impact of severity factors that mediate (or moderate) therapeutic impact on outcome (**Fig.2B**).

Figure 2. A strategy for integration of multiple modalities using modern data science tools and analytic approaches. (A) Using multidimensional machine learning tools such as unsupervised manifold learning, it is possible to measure the project individual subjects into their unique position in the ‘syndromic space’ defined by the full set of pre-Clinical characteristics from injury biomechanics and acute behavior, Biomarkers, and Imaging. By pooling data across multiple experiments it becomes possible to understand the relative position of diverse types of injuries and stratify injury models based on severity. (B) The multidimensional injury severity index can then be used in causal testing of therapeutics as a mediator for precision medicine applications. A particular therapeutic dosing/timing (circle) would represent an independent variable (X) and an *a priori* functional endpoint would serve as the outcome variable (green box, Y). The injury severity would serve as a mediator variable (pink square, M) that alters the weight of the therapeutic intervention in a systematic manner, and explain the precise injury conditions under which the therapeutic has maximal efficacy. Such an approach has great potential to inform translation by providing context of use for new therapeutics.

Causal analysis and mediation approaches are relatively common in the fields of epidemiology/biostatistics and are increasingly used as in modern precision medicine studies¹²⁹. However, at the time of writing, these approaches are rare in the preclinical TBI literature. One of the major hurdles to realizing the potential of multidimensional analytic approaches for TBI is that these types of analytical workflows are ‘data hungry’ and require large quantities of structured data in analytic-ready forms. As mentioned in the companion paper by Martone et al. (in press), the field now has a dedicated NIH-supported repository, the Open Data Commons for TBI that helps in this goal. We are beginning to see examples of big-data approaches to preclinical TBI research that align to trends in clinical TBI^{66,119,130}. An important clarification is that the development and application of a multidimensional injury severity index represent distinct phases with different data requirements. While the initial construction and validation of such a scale may require large, aggregated datasets spanning hundreds or thousands of subjects to reliably define weighting and structure across domains, once established, the application of the resulting severity framework to individual animals or small laboratory cohorts is no longer inherently data intensive. In this setting, investigators can project the measures they routinely collect onto a shared severity space, yielding an interpretable severity estimate even when only a subset of variables is available. Critically, as community-scale data resources grow, these models can be trained to optimally leverage partial or heterogeneous inputs, enabling individual laboratories to contextualize their injuries relative to the broader field without requiring

uniform data collection. In this way, large-scale data integration serves not only to improve model fidelity but also to democratize access to more informative severity estimation, benefiting both resource-limited laboratories and the translational value of shared datasets.

There are a few early examples of applications of machine learning (ML) and advanced analytics to help integrate complex multidimensional data about TBI in both preclinical models^{66,131,132} and human data^{130,133,134}. These approaches focus on capturing the multivariate impact of injury severity. For example, Nielson et al., 2015 used manifold ML and topological data analysis to synthesize data from multiple endpoints to visualize the full ‘syndromic disease space’ of TBI and polytrauma (**Figure 3**). Nielson et al built on prior work in the machine intelligence literature focused on fusing complex information by considering individual variables to be imperfect windows into an underlying manifold, or multidimensional shape, that defines the underlying structure of an intercorrelated data system. They then applied this approach to polytraumatic TBI combined with spinal cord injury (SCI), demonstrating that the anatomical location of polytrauma is a profound modifier of TBI outcome at the multidimensional level (**Fig.3E**). Additional reports utilizing data from the OBTT consortium further illustrate the feasibility and utility of ML strategies in the preclinical TBI setting^{135,136}. In this case, supervised ML classifiers were applied to large, multicenter, and multi-TBI model rodent datasets to identify recovery profiles and distinguish treatment effects based on complex combinations of behavioral, histological, and biomarker features, highlighting how data-driven models can extract meaningful patterns even when individual variables are imperfect predictors.

Figure 3. Example of a data-driven machine intelligence approach applied to complex models of polytraumatic TBI with SCI using topological manifold learning. (A) In this type of data analysis, analysts first define the metric space for all of the variables, defining whether categorical, ordinal, or numeric

and applies optimal scaling cross-correlation among all variables constructing a giant cross-correlation matrix. (B) Applying mathematical 'lenses' to the correlation matrix, machine intelligence tools build a projection of individual subjects into multidimensional manifold space based on their unique score on each of the variables. This defines the 'syndromic space' of TBI. (C) Then, using advanced clustering algorithms it is possible to resample the space thousands of times with different sized bins to extract consistent clusters of individuals reflecting the syndromic manifold that can be projected down to a two dimensional map. (D) Two dimensional 'map' of multidimensional similarity of individual subjects, taking into account information across hundreds of variables simultaneously. (E) Navigating the syndromic space by mapping injury condition onto the space reveals the counterintuitive finding that ipsilateral TBI and SCI produces a unique profile of improved function not seen in the other forms of polytrauma. Modified from⁶⁶.

Integrating Machine Learning and Human Knowledge Approaches

One challenge associated with some data-driven ML approaches is that the internal logic by which models arrive at predictions or representations may be difficult for humans to interpret, particularly for complex, highly parameterized algorithms (e.g., neural networks). In the context of supervised classification or prediction tasks, this "black box" behavior can obscure biological interpretation and motivates the use of established reporting and validation frameworks (e.g., TRIPOD and TRIPOD-AI) to ensure transparency, reproducibility, and appropriate model evaluation. As a result, meaningful biological interpretation, for example, determining whether a conclusion drawn from a ML approach is biologically relevant, typically emerges from an iterative process in which model outputs are examined and contextualized by domain experts, balancing predictive performance with mechanistic plausibility.

Distinct from these analytic applications, emerging generative AI tools such as large language models (LLMs) are not designed to infer injury severity or model biological processes directly, but instead operate by generating text based on statistical patterns in large textual training databases. While such tools may be useful for organizing information or facilitating knowledge discovery, they are susceptible to producing inaccurate or non-verifiable outputs ("hallucinations") that could mislead us in our quest to understand TBI injury severity. For this reason, there is a strong need to apply steps to integrate human knowledge and semantics with ML/AI tools. This approach is known as 'expert augmented ML' and is characterized by explicit steps to work with ML approaches to ensure that model outputs are interpretable by humans and explainable to other researchers, clinicians, and regulators alike^{131,137}. Toward this end, efforts are underway to create a formal ontology for characterizing pre-clinical models of TBI. Ontologies provide a means for capturing human knowledge in a way that it can be processed by computers to draw the same types of inferences as a human expert. The Brain Injury Knowledge Ontology (BIKO) (RRID:SCR_024628) is working to define injury model types and assessments based on an accounting of their inputs and outputs that facilitates relating different parameters to injury severity (Surles-Zeigler et al., this issue). The power of pairing data-driven (syndromics) and knowledge-driven (ontologies) is well known in the genomics field where ontology enrichment analyses using the Gene Ontology (RRID:SCR_002811) are standard for identifying categories of molecular types, cell components, or biological functions that are enriched in a given gene cluster.

Conclusion

Decades of research have contributed to how clinicians manage TBI patients. Although novel pharmacological interventions have largely failed to translate from preclinical models to effective clinical therapies, substantial improvements in long-term patient outcomes have been achieved through advances in surgical and ICU protocols. Notably, preclinical research has contributed substantially to these gains. For example, discoveries in preclinical models contributed to major advances including identifying novel biomarkers to triage patients who may require further neuroimaging or surgical intervention, developing decision trees and tiers of intervention to help manage intracranial pressure, evaluating the consequences of a smaller versus larger craniotomy, and the development of technologies that help us identify and manage many of the complications that occur in the acute hospital and neuroICU. These successes highlight the potential for us to do better as we translate findings from the bench-to-bedside. There is growing evidence that the crude characterization of severity as mild, moderate, or severe based on GCS trichotomization alone has significant limitations for prognostication. When one doesn't incorporate biological mechanism or likelihood of patient recovery into the design of clinical trials, it can lead to the rejection of interventions that might benefit a specific population of TBI patients. By applying a framework, whether CBI-M or perhaps something even more information-rich the future, we may significantly improve both prognostication and clinical trial design. By incorporating high resolution multimodal measurement, CBI-M may help determine individuals who are going to have a full recovery and provide targeted precision therapeutics to those who will benefit most. Similarly, taking steps in the laboratory to move away from traditional descriptions of mild, moderate, and severe TBI and instead focusing more on clinically-aligned, multidimensional endpoint monitoring will open opportunities for integrative data-driven approaches to classify injury harnessing ML/AI tools. Fusing these approaches with formal knowledge representation will allow us to better describe the differences in the underlying biology following diffuse versus focal TBI, and identify which markers best predict recovery of function (whether learning and memory, executive, motor function or even sleep). Ultimately, the goal is to matching therapies, whether re-purposed, re-evaluated or novel, to the individual model or the individual translationally-relevant phenotype. If we can do this in the laboratory, we will increase our odds of moving interventions from the laboratory setting to the bedside to improve patient care after TBI.

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